

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Gbadoe****FIRST NAME: Melinda****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is using someone else's words or ideas without crediting the author.¹**
- Plagiarism is using overly complicated vocabulary.
- Plagiarism is writing papers without consulting the instructor.
- Plagiarism is citing sources too frequently in your work.

2. What punctuation is used to introduce a subclause that logically follows from the main clause?

- Semicolon (;)

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- Comma (,)
 - Colon (:)**²
 - Apostrophe (')
3. Which step is recommended before editing an essay to improve its quality dramatically?
- Put the essay aside for a few days before editing.**³
 - Immediately submit the first draft without any editing.
 - Begin editing as soon as you finish writing.
 - Only edit the conclusion, ignoring the introduction and body paragraphs.
4. What does "alignment" ensure in qualitative research?
- Fast completion of dissertation.
 - Enhanced creativity in dissertation writing.
 - Increased number of research participants.
 - Methodological integrity and congruence throughout the dissertation.**⁴
5. Which of the following is one primary purpose of a literature review in a qualitative dissertation?

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 18.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 11.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, 2019), 123–125.

- Situating the research problem within a broader academic conversation.**⁵
- Confirming personal beliefs of the researcher.
- Describing each article separately without integration.
- Establishing direct interviews with all authors mentioned.
6. When is the main literature review conducted in a grounded theory study?
- Exclusively after all data analysis is complete.
- Primarily during concept development to define and clarify theoretical relationships.**⁶
- Only before data collection begins.
- After the dissertation defense.
7. What is the primary purpose of writing a dissertation concept paper?
- To describe what might be studied in the dissertation, why it needs to be studied, and how it might be studied.**⁷
- To defend the dissertation methodology to the university.
- To summarize the research after it has been completed.
- To outline all future academic publications based on the dissertation research.
8. What is meant by a study's "social significance"?

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 176–77.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 176–77.

⁷ James P. Sampson, Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2–3.

- The statistical strength of research outcomes.
- The popularity of the research topic among doctoral students.
- The total number of participants involved in the research study.
- Solving the research problem is important because of its potential positive impact on society.⁸**

9. What is the correct way to structure a research argument according to Turabian?

- It involves persuading the audience through emotional appeals rather than evidence.
- It involves making a claim supported by reasons and evidence, acknowledging objections, and establishing relevance clearly.⁹**
- It primarily relies on intuition and personal feeling.
- It consists of stating claims without anticipating reader objections or questions.

10. Why should authors restate their claim in the conclusion, according to Turabian?

- To clearly reaffirm the claim and offer readers a new significance or practical application derived from the research.¹⁰**
- To repeat the introduction word-for-word and reinforce ideas through redundancy.
- To introduce entirely new and unrelated claims.

⁸ Sampson, *Guide to Dissertation Research*, 30.

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed., rev. Wayne C. Booth et al. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 56–57.

¹⁰ Turabian et al., *Manual for Writers*, 107–108.

- To avoid summarizing the main arguments, introduce unrelated issues instead.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.